

Vietnamese University Lecturers Apply AI in Teaching. A Case Study in Thu Dau Mot University

Tạ Thị Thanh Loan
Thu Dau Mot University, Viet Nam

Nguyễn Thị Hương Thủy
Thu Dau Mot University, Viet Nam

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Abstract:

AI plays an increasingly important role in the education sector, especially in teaching, thanks to its outstanding features that help personalize the learning experience, support teachers and increase teaching efficiency. Lecturers are taking advantage of AI to improve the learning experience, from building curriculum, personalizing learning paths for each student, to using virtual teaching assistants to help answer questions. AI also helps analyze learning data to predict learning efficiency, detect students' difficulties early, thereby providing timely support. Through in-depth interviews, group discussions, document analysis and case studies at Thu Dau Mot

University (TDMU), the article presents AI applications in teaching at universities and evaluates the effectiveness of using AI in teaching activities. Research on AI applications in teaching at TDMU has brought many valuable findings, helping to clarify the potential, benefits and challenges of this technology in higher education in Vietnam, AI helps build personalized learning paths, supporting students according to their own needs and levels, thereby improving learning efficiency.

Keywords: *AI applications, teaching, efficiency, tools.*

Introduction

Artificial intelligence (AI) is developing at a rapid pace and is playing an increasingly important role in many areas of life. This progress comes from breakthroughs in machine learning, natural language processing (NLP), and computer vision, allowing AI to not only understand but also respond, analyze, and perform many complex tasks that were previously only possible for humans.

In the field of education, AI can analyze each student's learning data to provide appropriate learning content and methods, thereby helping students understand lessons better and develop

in their own way. Online learning platforms use AI to deliver automated classes, analyze student weaknesses, and tailor teaching content accordingly. AI can also act as a virtual assistant, helping to answer questions, automatically grade papers, and reduce the workload for teachers. Artificial intelligence has been creating powerful changes in all aspects of life, contributing to improving work efficiency, creating smart solutions and helping people save time and resources. With endless potential, AI promises to play an even more important role in the future, not only in education but also in all other fields.

The application of AI in teaching is becoming increasingly necessary to improve the quality of education and better meet the increasingly diverse learning needs of students. In the context of a rapidly changing world with the strong development of technology and an increasing amount of information, the use of AI not only helps improve teaching efficiency but also helps students have a richer and more personalized learning experience.

The aim of the paper is to present applications of AI in teaching at universities and evaluate the effectiveness of using AI in teaching activities, case study in Thu Dau Mot University.

Literature Review

In recent years, AI (artificial intelligence) has become a prominent research area in education, with the aim of improving the quality of learning and teaching. Research on AI in education focuses not only on developing the technology but also on how this technology can create profound changes in the learning process, helping to personalize education and enhance the student experience.

Hana Truong (2023) in the study "ChatGPT and Education: Overview of Research Situation in the World and Vietnam" introduced an overview of the research situation on ChatGPT in the field of education globally and in Vietnam. Global and Vietnamese research focuses on the capabilities of the ChatGPT model as well as the potential and challenges in education. The article emphasizes the need for clear policies and regulations on the use of technology in education, as well as the importance of understanding the limitations of ChatGPT and encouraging critical thinking and independent analysis skills. By leveraging the potential of ChatGPT and artificial intelligence tools, we can improve the quality of teaching and learning experiences and build a more interactive and effective educational environment.

Nguyen Lam Ngoc Vi and NLNV (2023) in the study "Exploring the impact of Artificial Intelligence in higher education: Applications and challenges": The study investigates the

application of Artificial Intelligence in Education (AIEd) in higher education. Research is conducted on AIEd applications such as intelligent tutoring systems, adaptive learning systems, policy-making advisors, and smart learning tools to improve the learning experience, performance, and quality for both students and teachers. The purpose of these applications is to provide customized and individualized learning experiences, enhance learning outcomes, and aid education administrators in making informed decisions. In addition, the study demonstrates that incorporating AI in higher education poses challenges that must be addressed, such as ensuring data privacy and security, ethical concerns, negative perceptions of AI, and a technology gap between teaching and learning participants, as well as some recommendations for addressing these issues in the field of education.

Doan Thi Van (2024) in the study "Artificial Intelligence and its application in designing videos to support teaching of Natural and Social subjects for grade 3" emphasized that: applying AI to design learning videos will bring many breakthroughs in the teaching and learning process. Besides, Natural and Social subjects play an important role in education. The topics revolve around many contents close to daily life, requiring teachers to design appropriate and attractive teaching and learning activities based on exploiting students' life experiences. Therefore, it is possible to apply AI to design videos to support teaching and learning to meet the requirements of the 2018 General Education program. On this basis, the article studies AI and its application in teaching, thereby proposing the process of designing videos and applying them to Natural and Social subjects for grade 3.

MA Chaudhry and E. Kazim (2022), F. Ouyang, L. Zheng, and P. Jiao (2022), H. Pham, QN Tran, GL La, HM Doan, and TD Vu (2021), NTT Dung (2021), M. Akour and M. Alenezi (2022), M. Alenezi (2023), V. Niță and I. Guțu (2023), ect: The studies of these authors show that personalizing learning paths helps students progress faster and achieve better results. AI helps create learning programs tailored to each

individual based on their abilities and needs. Studies explore how AI can help create interactive learning environments that encourage active student participation through tools such as chatbots, virtual assistants, and learning platforms. Research in this area focuses on using AI to automate tasks such as grading and assessment, reducing the workload on teachers and increasing the accuracy and timeliness of feedback to students. Many studies develop AI tools to support students with learning difficulties or special learning needs, helping them integrate better.

Research on AI in education is opening up new opportunities and helping to improve the quality of education in a sustainable way. With diverse AI methods and tools, the field is contributing to personalizing and optimizing the learning experience, while preparing students with the skills needed in the 21st century.

Studies have highlighted the importance of AI in society, in education, especially in higher education. Thereby, it has also pointed out the impact of AIED on universities in the world, in some countries and in Vietnam. This article inherits the assessments of the impact of AI in education, the paper presents the applications of AI in teaching at universities and evaluates the effectiveness of using AI in teaching activities.

Methods

In-depth interviews: Interview university lecturers to understand their experiences and perspectives on applying AI in teaching. Prepare semi-structured questions to allow lecturers to freely share.

Focus groups: Organize focus groups with multiple faculty, students, or experts in the education and technology fields. This helps gather diverse perspectives.

Document content analysis: Research related documents, reports and other research articles on the application of AI in teaching in Vietnam and around the world.

Case Study: Thu Dau Mot University is selected for detailed analysis. This method helps to

deeply research the implementation methods, benefits and practical challenges when applying AI in the educational environment.

Results

Applications of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in Teaching at Universities

AI is now widely applied in teaching at universities, bringing many benefits in improving teaching and learning efficiency. Below are some typical applications of AI in the higher education environment:

Support personalized learning. AI can analyze each student's learning behavior, ability, and progress to make appropriate recommendations. This helps create a personalized learning path that suits each student's ability and pace. AI systems can automatically generate personalized learning materials, review questions, and tests for students, helping them learn proactively and in an organized manner.

Virtual tutoring system. Chatbots can answer students' frequently asked questions, assist in finding study materials, and provide information about lectures, schedules, and class activities. AI can automatically grade simple tests, especially those with multiple choice or short answer questions. These assistants help teachers save time and reduce work pressure.

Enhance learning experiences through AR/VR technology and simulations. AI can help create virtual reality simulations for students to practice in fields like medicine, engineering, and science. This is especially useful for subjects that require hands-on experience, giving students experience in a safe and controlled environment. AI combined with virtual reality (VR) technology enables the creation of intuitive learning environments that allow students to explore and learn in a vibrant and engaging way.

Support remote teaching and classroom management. AI tools can record, annotate, and translate lectures in real-time, making it easy for students to access knowledge and not miss important details. AI can help instructors monitor student learning and engagement,

identify students who show signs of needing early support, and manage grades and assessments.

Data analysis and assessment of learning outcomes. AI can track and analyze student progress in real-time, providing early warnings if students are struggling and need support. AI tools have the ability to automatically evaluate assignments and multiple-choice tests, helping instructors save grading time and minimize errors due to manual grading.

Support research and development of teaching content. AI makes it easier for teachers and students to search and synthesize information from academic sources. Text analytics tools can also categorize, summarize, and extract important information. AI can suggest and recommend new topics, materials, and teaching methods, helping instructors update teaching content easily and effectively.

In general, the application of AI in teaching at universities helps to significantly improve the quality of education, optimize management processes and learning support, and create a more friendly and effective learning environment for both lecturers and students.

Evaluating the Effectiveness of Using AI in Teaching Activities at Thu Dau Mot University

Through interviews with a number of lecturers at Thu Dau Mot University (TDMU) to understand their experiences and perspectives when applying AI in teaching. Below is a summary of some interview results from lecturers at (TDMU) about their experiences and perspectives when applying AI in teaching. This information provides a multi-dimensional view of the benefits, challenges and expectations of lecturers when applying AI in teaching and learning activities:

Benefits of Applying AI in Teaching

Personalized learning: Many instructors say AI helps them personalize instruction for each student, especially in large classes. One IT instructor commented that AI helps identify struggling students and provide appropriate supplementary materials.

Increased teaching efficiency: AI reduces the time spent on administrative tasks, such as grading quizzes or organizing lectures, allowing instructors to focus more on interacting directly with students.

Improving the quality of learning materials: Instructors said they use AI to synthesize information, suggest new materials, and make lectures more up-to-date and relevant to reality. Some instructors appreciate AI's ability to support information retrieval, helping to enrich lecture content.

Challenges in AI Application

Lack of in-depth knowledge of AI: Some faculty, especially in fields not directly related to the technology, said they had difficulty getting started with learning about and applying AI. They felt they needed more training and support to use the technology effectively.

Cost and limited resources: A lecturer in the Faculty of Economics said that AI tools and the resources needed to implement them are often quite expensive. The university needs to invest more to provide appropriate AI tools and technology infrastructure to lecturers.

Security and privacy: Some faculty members are concerned about the security of student data when using AI tools. They believe that the collection and processing of personal data must strictly comply with privacy regulations to avoid security risks.

Views and Expectations about the Future of AI Applications in Teaching

Wider AI adoption: Most faculty expect AI to be more widely deployed in classrooms and disciplines. They expect AI to improve student access to knowledge, enhance the learning experience, and promote student engagement in learning.

Institutional Support: Faculty expressed a desire for more AI-related policies, resources, and training from their institutions. They wanted support from on-campus AI experts, as well as access to higher-quality materials and tools.

Teaching innovation: Some teachers, especially young teachers, believe that AI will drive

innovation in teaching methods, making the classroom more interactive and flexible. They expect to be able to experiment with new teaching methods, such as flipped classrooms or blended learning, with the help of AI.

Typical AI Applications Used by Lecturers

Learning Management Systems: Some instructors have used AI built into learning management systems (LMS) to automatically track student progress and provide automated assessments.

Chatbots to support students: Some departments have begun experimenting with using chatbots to help students with lecture questions and common learning problems.

Learning data analytics: Some instructors use AI tools to analyze student learning data, which can then be used to evaluate the effectiveness of teaching methods and adjust content accordingly.

Suggestions from Lecturers

In-depth training: The lecturer suggested that the school organize in-depth training courses, suitable for each field, so that all lecturers are able to apply AI effectively.

Resource and equipment support: Provide additional resources and equipment needed, such as AI software, more powerful computing infrastructure to run complex AI applications, making AI more accessible and usable for instructors.

Develop a support policy: Lecturers want to have a clear privacy policy to feel secure using AI in teaching, especially when dealing with students' personal data.

Overall, TDMU lecturers have a positive perception of AI applications in teaching, despite some challenges. Support from the university, along with additional investment in technology and training, will help lecturers make the most of AI's potential in education.

Organize focus group discussions with many lecturers and students of TDMU:

The results of the focus group discussion with TDMU lecturers and students on the

effectiveness of using AI in teaching and learning provided many multi-dimensional perspectives, clarifying the benefits as well as challenges in the process of implementing AI. Below are the main opinions obtained:

Benefits of AI in teaching and learning activities. Many lecturers agree that AI helps create personalized learning paths for each student. This helps them categorize students according to their level of understanding and provide appropriate support for each individual. Some lecturers find AI useful in automatically assessing students' learning progress and helping struggling students earlier. Lecturers say that AI helps them reduce the time spent on administrative tasks, such as grading, summarizing results, and planning lessons. This allows lecturers to focus more on improving teaching methods and enhancing the quality of interactions with students. Some lecturers say that AI-supported interactive activities such as simulations, educational games, and virtual reality (VR/AR) learning have helped students become more interested and gain a deeper understanding of complex topics. AI also helps create realistic learning scenarios, especially in fields such as medicine and engineering, where hands-on learning is highly required.

Student feedback: Students appreciate the personalization of AI because they can control their own learning progress, learn at their own pace, and access materials that are appropriate for their abilities. Students report feeling less pressured and having more time to review and improve their skills thanks to AI-powered learning recommendations. Students appreciate the ability of AI assistants and chatbots to quickly answer simple questions and provide learning materials. This gives students more time to focus on their studies and minimizes the disruption of waiting for a response from the instructor. Additionally, students find that interactive activities help them absorb lessons more easily and feel more engaged with the content. Technologies like VR/AR, when combined with AI, bring lectures to life, allowing students to practice in a safe and fun simulated environment.

Challenges in using AI in teaching and learning . Some lecturers believe that the cost of AI tools, resources and equipment is quite high, and not all departments have full access to these technologies. This leads to differences in teaching quality between disciplines. Some lecturers, especially from social sciences, feel less confident in using AI tools and wish for more training on how to apply AI in teaching. This will help lecturers not only use AI proficiently but also exploit the full potential of the technology.

Students also shared that not all of them have the right equipment to use AI applications, especially when using VR/AR technologies or software that requires high computer configuration. Students asked the school to provide more support in terms of equipment and infrastructure. Some students said that they need time to get used to new AI tools and sometimes feel pressured when using them. Students wanted more detailed instructions and hands-on opportunities to improve their technology skills.

Security and privacy: Both faculty and students expressed concerns about data security when applying AI, especially personal data and learning outcomes. They said that data collection needs to comply with strict regulations to protect student privacy. Faculty also suggested that schools need to have clear and strict policies on data protection and privacy when applying AI.

Expectations for the future of AI applications . Both lecturers and students expect schools to invest more in AI infrastructure and technology, making it easier and more equitable for everyone to access this technology. They suggest that schools should provide more AI equipment, resources, and software tools to optimally support learning and teaching activities. Lecturers and students suggest that schools organize AI-related training programs and workshops to help lecturers and students develop the necessary skills to use AI effectively. These courses should include both theory and practice, from basic to advanced, to suit a variety of levels and needs.

Create flexible and effective AI-integrated learning environments . Teachers want AI to be

integrated into new teaching methods such as flipped classrooms or blended learning. Students also expressed their desire for more interactive lessons and tests through AI, helping them learn and test their knowledge in a more vivid way.

Overall, the opinions during the discussion showed a consensus on the potential of AI to enhance the quality of teaching and learning at TDMU, while also pointing out the challenges that need to be addressed. Recommendations for the university on investment in technology, training and security policies will play an important role in creating a modern, effective and sustainable educational environment.

Discussion

The research results on the effectiveness of using AI in teaching at TDMU are of great significance, not only helping to understand the potential and impact of AI in higher education in Vietnam but also contributing to supplementing and clarifying global trends.

The fact that both TDMU lecturers and students highly appreciate the personalization capabilities of AI shows that AI has great potential in supporting each student according to their own path and needs, improving the quality of learning and optimizing the teaching process. AI's ability to automatically analyze and make learning recommendations helps lecturers detect students' difficulties and intervene promptly, minimizing learning lag.

Previous research have demonstrated that AI can improve learning efficiency through personalization, helping students develop self-learning skills and enhancing learning experiences (Nguyen Ngoc Lam Vi, 2023). The results of the study at TDMU are consistent with these results, emphasizing that personalization is not only beneficial for students at developed universities but also effective at Vietnamese educational institutions.

The study was conducted only at TDMU with a limited number of lecturers and students, leading to the results not fully reflecting the views of all lecturers and students in Vietnam. This may reduce the generalizability of the study,

especially when applied to other universities with different scales or characteristics. In addition, the data was collected over a specific period of time, so the results may only reflect the experiences and views of lecturers and students at that time. Rapid changes in AI technology can affect the effectiveness and user experience, so the study may not fully reflect long-term AI application trends. This study may not have analyzed each specific industry in depth, leading to difficulty in assessing the impact of AI on each industry group clearly and specifically.

The majority of data from this study was collected through interviews and focus groups, which are primarily qualitative in nature. While this approach provides a deep understanding of participants' opinions and perspectives, the lack of quantitative data may limit the ability to accurately and systematically assess the impact of AI.

To increase the generalizability of the results, future studies should include more universities across the country, especially those of different sizes and disciplines. This would help compare the differences in AI attitudes and effectiveness across schools, thereby providing a more comprehensive view of AI application in higher education in Vietnam.

Further studies should be conducted over a longer period of time to track changes in attitudes and effectiveness of AI over time. Qualitative methods such as in-depth interviews should be combined with quantitative methods such as large-scale surveys to obtain more diverse and rich data. Quantitative methods will help to accurately measure the impact of AI on each aspect of learning and teaching, thereby producing more reliable results. To understand the impact of AI in each specific field, further studies should delve into different disciplines, analyzing the impact of AI on the specific teaching and learning characteristics of each discipline. For example, research in medicine and engineering could focus on AI applications in practice and simulation, while research in social sciences could focus on tools to support information analysis and synthesis.

Conclusion

Research on AI applications in teaching at TDMU has brought many valuable findings, helping to clarify the potential, benefits and challenges of this technology in higher education in Vietnam. Highlights from the study: AI helps build personalized learning paths, supporting students according to their own needs and levels, thereby improving learning efficiency. Students can control their own progress, receive timely support, and feel more connected to the learning content. This is an important factor, contributing to increasing students' self-study ability and helping lecturers detect students' difficulties early to provide timely support. This study has contributed to building a knowledge base on AI applications in higher education in Vietnam, providing practical data from Thu Dau Mot University and presenting highly applicable results for other universities. The study also contributes to consolidating and supplementing international studies on the effectiveness of AI in teaching, emphasizing the potential of AI in enhancing personalization and interaction in the learning process.

To further explore the application of AI in university teaching, future studies can consider the following suggestions to expand and improve the effectiveness of AI application in higher education: Comparing the effectiveness of AI tools by field and subject; Assessing the skills and awareness of lecturers and students about AI; Analyzing factors affecting the acceptance of AI in teaching; Analyzing the costs and benefits of applying AI in education; Learning about AI applications in assessment and testing; etc.

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